

IEC 61400-15 Working Group

Progress Update – Meeting 10

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Boulder, Colorado - USA

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1. Introduction

The IEC 61400-15 Working Group (WG) is developing an IEC standard for wind resource assessment, energy yield analysis and site suitability input estimation (the Standard). The working group is convened by Bob Sherwin (EAPC – USA), and the Secretary is Jason Fields (NREL – USA). The WG is comprised of 58 topic-area experts from 15 countries, including representatives from developers, turbine manufacturers, consultancies, labs, and academia. A list of WG members and Meeting 10 Attendees is available from the convener. This document presents a summary of the Standard's IEC TC-88 approved scope. It also provides an update on the status of the Standard development as of WG Meeting 10, held 24 – 27 January, 2017 in Boulder, Colorado. This is not an official IEC document; it is a product solely of this working group. The aim of this document is to share the status of the Standard's development.

2. Scope of the Standard - IEC TC-88 Approved

The scope of the 61400-15 Standard is to define a framework for assessment and reporting of the wind resource, energy yield and site suitability input conditions for both onshore and offshore wind power plants. This includes:

1. Definition, measurement, and prediction of the long-term meteorological and wind flow characteristics at the site
2. Integration of the long-term meteorological and wind flow characteristics with wind turbine and balance of plant characteristics to predict net energy yield
3. Characterizing environmental extremes and other relevant plant design drivers
4. Assessing the uncertainty associated with each of these steps
5. Addressing documentation and reporting requirements to help ensure the traceability of the assessment processes

The framework will be defined such that applicable national norms are considered and industry best practices are utilized.

The meteorological and wind flow characteristics addressed in this document relate to wind conditions, where parameters such as wind speed, wind direction, air density or air temperature are included to the extent that they affect the operation and structural integrity of a wind turbine (WTGS) and energy production analysis.

According to IEC 61400-1 and 61400-3 the site-specific conditions can be broken down into wind conditions, other environmental conditions, soil conditions, ocean/lake conditions and electrical conditions. All of these site conditions other than site-specific wind conditions and related documents are out of scope for this Standard.

3. Aim of the Standard

This Standard is framed to complement and support the scope of related IEC 61400 series standards by defining environmental input conditions. It is not intended to supersede the design and suitability requirements presented in those standards. Specific analytical and modeling procedures as described in IEC 61400-1, 61400-2, and 61400-3 are excluded from this scope.

The basic and fundamental goal is to present consensus methodologies on site assessment and to create a set of standard reporting requirements which detail the measurement campaign, analysis processes, and considerations taken by the author of a wind resource characterization and energy yield assessment. The methodologies presented provide a framework to ensure a high quality set of project data are collected and analyzed to support wind resource and site characterization. The standardized reporting process will provide a discrete list of criteria, which must be considered and reported on for all projects. These reporting procedures will provide transparency to report readers about the considerations taken during the analysis, and confidence that the analysis considered all of the key criteria and procedures identified by IEC 61400-15 for wind resource assessment.

At a minimum, the document will prescribe standard reporting elements and considerations during the analysis process, and recommend practices to reduce uncertainty for all elements of the assessment and campaign.

Two additional goals of the Standard, which should be explored by the committee:

- Develop a standard uncertainty calculation to be used for benchmarking
- Provide standardized inputs for turbine loads calculations

The document will not:

- Qualify or disqualify projects
- Qualify or disqualify consultants/Independent Engineers

4. Working Group Progress Update – Meeting 10

This section presents a summary of the WG's approach and progress as of 27 January 2017. Information here has consensus among the WG participants, but is subject to review and revision. It is NOT officially approved or sanctioned by the IEC.

A report certified to the 61400-15 Standard will comply with a standard reporting format and uncertainty framework. The quality and accuracy of the underlying analysis and results will then be more easily evaluated and omissions clearly identified. A compliant report is expected to provide sufficient information for an independent assessor to evaluate the processes and results.

4.1. Working Group Structure and Approach

The WG has divided up the Standard development work into the initial topic-area packages:

- Site suitability inputs
- Uncertainties
- Reporting

Each of the uncertainty topic areas was assigned sub-groups to address the contributing parameters, and associated reporting requirements. Specifically, each sub-group is working to define:

- Descriptions

- Drivers
- A normal range of expected values
- A default model for calculating the uncertainty

An additional sub-group is working to define methods to combine uncertainties

Varying degrees of progress have been made within each of the sub-groups. The following sections describe the content that was sufficiently advanced for external review.

4.2. Energy Yield

The WG has identified approaches to energy assessment based upon each of (or a combination of) the following:

1. Wind measurements
2. Production data
3. Virtual data (mesoscale model)

Work has focused on establishing a loss and uncertainty framework to cover assessment approaches 1 and 2. Assessment approach 3 or more complex hybrid analyses have yet to be addressed by the working group.

Table 1 below shows the loss register framework. Table 2 shows the high level uncertainty categories associated with a wind measurement based analysis, with Tables 2.1 to 2.6 showing the sub-level categorization.

Production data from wind turbines in operation (reference wind turbines) may serve as “site specific wind and energy information” and can be applied to verify the estimated wind and/or energy potential for the prospective site. In such a case site-specific wind measurements may not be necessary. The uncertainty framework of this approach is below in Table 3, with Tables 3.1 to 3.6 showing the sub-level categorization.

The ongoing work of the group is to establish methodologies to quantify and combine the uncertainties for both wind based and production based uncertainties, and to define the reporting requirements against each analysis. For cases where both production data and wind measurements are available the uncertainty formulation would involve some combination of wind based and production based frameworks, and this has yet to be defined.

4.3. Site Suitability

Wind turbines are subject to environmental and electrical conditions including the influence of nearby turbines, which affect their loading, durability and operation. This work focuses on the climatic conditions as required by IEC 61400-1 for the assessment of wind turbine site suitability. This includes the relevant wind parameters, the parameters that describe the topographical complexity, and the cold climate conditions. Effort has been focused on how to report these input parameters and their associated uncertainties to allow the manufactures to undertake site suitability calculations

A digital exchange format (DEF) is being developed to communicate the input parameters necessary for site suitability review and/or mechanical load assessment. This exchange format deals with project information, turbine layout, average and extreme wind conditions, turbulence intensity and its standard deviation, temperature, shear, inflow angle, terrain complexity, and related parameters. The format has been designed to be comprehensive in nature and aims to replace individual manufacturers' site suitability forms, allowing a developer or third party to complete the form once and issue the data to multiple manufactures. A graphical representation of the DEF's intended function is presented in Figure 1. The DEF does not exclude the use or consideration of the underlying wind and site data for suitability inputs, which will be at the discretion of the turbine OEM or developer.

The Standard will also prescribe a narrative report format to accompany the DEF, which should describe the methods employed to complete the inputs and calculate the uncertainties.

Informative methods for calculating all suitability input parameters, and associated uncertainties, will be provided. Where there is consensus, the methods will be standardized.

Figure 1: Site Suitability Input Digital Exchange Format (DEF) Sharing Concept

4.4. Offshore

Offshore atmospheric conditions, including those described in 61400-3, will be considered in each topic area and recommended variations will be presented where necessary.

5. Working Group Next Steps

The WG will continue developing uncertainty calculation methods for each of the categories described above. Reporting requirements for energy yield and suitability input analyses will also be developed further.

The next meeting for the WG is planned for the week of 12 - 16 June, 2017 in Porto, Portugal. Presentations and/or discussions of WG progress are anticipated to be held at various Industry events in the interim.

Table 1: Loss Framework

Wake Effect	
Internal Wake Effects	Wake effects internal to the wind plant
External Wake Effects	Wake effects generated externally to the wind plant
Future Wake Effects	Wake effects that will impact future energy projections based upon either confirmed or predicted new project development or decommissioning
Availability	
Turbine Availability	Turbine availability (energy-based), considering: Warranted availability, non-contractual availability, Restart after grid outage, Site Access, Downtime (or speed) to energy ratio, First Year / Plant start-up Availability
Balance of Plant Availability	Availability of substation and collection system, Other non-turbine availability, Warranted Availability, Site Access, First Year / Plant start-up
Grid Availability	Grid being outside Grid connection agreement operational parameters, actual grid downtime, delays in restart after grid outages.
Electrical	
Electrical Efficiency	Electrical losses between low or medium voltage side of the transformer of WTG(S) and the energy measurement point
Facility Parasitic Consumption	Turbine extreme weather packages, Other turbine and/or plant parasitic electrical losses (while operating or not operating)
Turbine Performance	
Sub-Optimal Performance	Performance deviations from the optimal wind plant performance due to software, instrumentation, and control setting issues
Generic Power Curve Adjustment	Expected deviation between advertised power curve and actual power performance in standard conditions (“inner range” ¹)
Site-specific Power Curve Adjustment	Accommodating for inclined flow, TI, density, shear, and other site / project-specific adjustments (“outer range” ¹)
High Wind Hysteresis	Energy lost in hysteresis loop between high wind speed cut-out and recut-in.
Environmental	
Icing	Performance degradation and shut down due to icing
Degradation	Blade fouling, efficiency losses, and other environmentally-driven performance degradation
Environmental Loss	High/low Temperature shut down or de-rate, Lightning, hail, and other environmental shut downs
Exposure	Tree growth or logging, other building development, etc.
Curtailements / Operational Strategies	
Load Curtailment	Speed and/or direction curtailments to mitigate loads
Grid Curtailment	PPA / off-taker curtailments, grid limitations
Environmental / Permit Curtailment	Birds, Bats, marine mammals, flicker, noise (when not captured in the power curve), etc.
Operational Strategies	Any periodic up-rating, down-rating, optimization or shut-down not captured in the power curve or availability carve-outs

¹ As defined by Power Curve Working group <http://www.pcwg.org>

Table 2: Uncertainty Framework – Wind Measurement Based Energy Yield

Primary Uncertainty Categories
Historical Wind Resource
Project Evaluation Period Variability
Measurement Uncertainty
Vertical Extrapolation
Horizontal Extrapolation
Plant Performance

Table 2.1: Measurement Based Uncertainty Categories - Historical Wind Resource

Historical Wind Resource	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Long-term Period:	What is the statistical representativeness of the chosen historical and/or site data period? I.e. the Inter-annual variability (coefficient of variation) of the historical reference data period in years.
Reference Data:	How accurate/reliable is the chosen reference data source? I.e. historical data consistency (e.g. is/are there possible underlying trend(s) in the data);
Long term adjustment:	What is the uncertainty associated with the prediction process? Statistical/empirical uncertainty in establishing a correlation or carrying out a prediction, which may be conditioned upon the correlation method and span/quantity of concurrent data period.
Wind Speed and Direction Distribution:	Mean wind speed aside, how representative is the measured/predicted distribution and wind/energy rose shape of the long-term? This makes most sense as an energy uncertainty term.
On-site Data Synthesis:	Uncertainty associated with gap-filling missing data periods. Usually done using directional correlations/MCP and, hence, long-term and reference data categories may apply.

Table 2.2: Measurement Based Uncertainty Categories - Project Evaluation Period Variability

Project Evaluation Period Variability	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Modelled Operational Period:	The statistical uncertainty associated with how closely the wind resource over the modelled operational period (i.e. 1-year, 10-year, etc.) may match the long-term site average.
Climate Change:	Where an impact of climate change can be assessed, then this may be considered as an uncertainty.
Plant Performance:	The statistical uncertainty associated with how closely the plant performance over the modelled operational period (i.e. 1-year, 10-year, etc.) may match the long-term site average.

Table 2.3: Measurement Based Uncertainty Categories - Measurement Uncertainties

Measurement Uncertainty	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Direct Measurement Uncertainties – those directly affecting the Measurement Uncertainty Category	
Wind Speed Measurement:	Including effects for Wind Speed Sensor Characteristics (Cup / sonic), Wind Speed Sensor Mounting / Deployment (Cup / sonic), Wind Speed Sensor Data Handling and Processing Characteristics (e.g. tower shadow, icing, degradation, etc.), System Motion, Consistency and Exposure, Data Acquisition, and Data Handling. Additionally, the reduction in uncertainty due to Sensor Combination is considered
Data Integrity and Documentation:	Documentation, Verification, and Traceability of the data
Indirect Measurement Uncertainties – those contributing to other uncertainty categories	
Wind Direction Measurement / Rose:	Sensor type/quality, Operational characteristics, Mounting Effects, Alignment, Acquisition, Long-term representativeness
Further atmospheric parameters:	Air Temperature, Pressure, Relative Humidity, and other atmospheric parameters

Table 2.4: Measurement Based Uncertainty Categories - Vertical Extrapolation

Vertical Extrapolation	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Model Inputs:	Terrain Surface Characterization, Wind data measurement height(s), wind statistic(s)/shear, measurement uncertainty
Model Components:	Representativeness per height/terrain, profile fit,
Model Stressor:	Large extrapolation distance, complex terrain (measurement height relative to terrain complexity)

Table 2.5: Measurement Based Uncertainty Categories - Horizontal Extrapolation

Horizontal Extrapolation	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Model Inputs:	Fidelity and appropriateness given sensitivity of model to - terrain data, roughness, forestry info, atmospheric conditions.
Model Stress:	Representativeness of initiation points relative to turbine locations in terms of complicating factors, e.g. Forestry, Stability, steep slopes, distance, elevation, veer. Intensity of and sensitivity to complicating factors
Model Appropriateness:	Physical scientific plausibility of model to capture complicating factors. Validation of implementation of model - published validation of specific implementation and relevance to complicating factors present on site. On-site model verification: site-to-site (un-tuned, blind) – consider quality of any shear verification also.

Table 2.6: Measurement Based Uncertainty Categories – Plant Performance

Plant Performance	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Wake Effect:	Uncertainties to cover all components and subcomponents of loss factors outlined in Table 1
Availability:	
Electrical:	
Turbine Performance:	
Environmental:	
Curtailments / Operational Strategies:	

Table 3: Uncertainty Framework – Production Data Based Energy Yield

Primary Uncertainty Categories
Historical Wind Resource
Project Evaluation Period Variability
Production Data
Vertical Extrapolation
Horizontal Extrapolation
Plant Performance

Table 3.1: Production Data Based Uncertainty Categories - Historical Wind Resource

Historical Wind Resource	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
See Table 2.1, Production Indexes also available.	

Table 3.2: Production Data Based Uncertainty Categories - Project Evaluation Period Variability

Project Evaluation Period Variability	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
See table 2.2	

Table 3.3: Production Data Based Uncertainty Categories – Production Data Uncertainties

Production Data Uncertainty	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Data:	Reliability of data source (Availability of Operational Reports, Availability of SCADA documentation), Data quality such as Data definition, integrity, temporal resolution, data recovery, turbine availability, length of data period and Point of measurement (WTG/grid connection point), Class of Uncertainty of the power metering equipment
Operation mode:	Reliability of information, Detail of information (restrictions, change in operation mode), Wake effects (Availability of information on external turbines).
Turbine performance:	Influence of site specific wind conditions, site-specific power curve, Spread of standard factory components on operating reference turbines
Data analysis:	Availability correction, Detection and handling of erroneous data
Representativeness for planned WTG:	Distance and elevation difference between reference turbine(s) and planned turbine(s), Surface characteristics, WTG type, Hub height, reference turbine layout and/or exposure

Table 3.4: Production Data Based Uncertainty Categories - Vertical Extrapolation

Vertical Extrapolation	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
Model Inputs:	Terrain Surface Characterization, reference turbines hub height(s), wind statistic(s)/shear, production data uncertainty.
Model Components:	Representativeness per height/terrain, profile fit,
Model Stressor:	Large extrapolation distance, complex terrain (reference turbine hub height relative to terrain complexity)

Table 3.5: Production Data Based Uncertainty Categories - Horizontal Extrapolation

Horizontal Extrapolation	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
See Table 2.5	

Table 3.6: Production Data Based Uncertainty Categories – Plant Performance

Plant Performance	
Sub-level	Notes/definition:
See Table 2.6	